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VISUAL CULTURE AS A FACTOR IN THE FORMATION OF INNOVATIVE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES: THE CASE OF THE KYIV NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF CULTURE AND ARTS

Oksana Koshelieva

Senior Lecturer,

ORCID: 0000-0002-1653-2103, e-mail: renisenb@ukr.net,

Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts,

36, Ye. Konovaltsia St., Kyiv, Ukraine, 01133

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Abstract

The purpose of the article is to characterise the essence of visual culture and determine its impact on audio visualisation and analyse the proof of its application in higher education institutions. The article also analyses the case of the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts in introducing innovative technologies in the educational process. The research methodology is based on the use of historical and theoretical analysis of pedagogical, philosophical, and art studies sources on the issue under study. Comparative and systematic approaches have helped to define visual culture as a factor in change and innovation shaping in the education system. The scientific novelty consists in studying the features of implementing the latest forms in the educational process, which are caused by changes in cultural priorities. Conclusions. The article proves that visual culture, becoming an integral part of modern society, a universal communicator, incentive of activity, a form of Contemporary Art, a means of education, plays a significant role in the formation of public opinion and active subjectification of various forms of social activity. Therefore, the urgent need for higher educational institutions is the use of leading pedagogical technologies. One of these technologies is audio visualisation, which is considered one of the most effective and motivating means to interact with the world of science. Therefore, its involvement and competent use in the educational process is not only a time requirement, and also a complex but necessary process.

We believe that the University has gained considerable practical experience in using digital tools thanks to the use of modern digital technologies, interactive tools of educational gamification, the options of Google Classroom, conducting workshops and video conferences in a state of lockdown, managed to combine traditional and innovative

technologies successfully; modern software tools, information resources and interaction of participants in the educational process.

▪ **Keywords:** visual culture; visualisation; audio visualisation; interactive teaching methods; higher education institution

▪ Introduction

The changes that are taking place today in the social, economic and educational spheres are caused by globalisation, high technologies, visual communications, information innovations, ergonomics, etc., and are naturally accompanied by a rethinking of values. In the teaching process, they are associated not only with humanisation and the humanistic orientation but also with the development of teaching technologies and the learning management. All this affects the nature of modern culture directly, the content and methods of knowledge transfer to the next generation. After all, today's student is a representative of a generation brought up under the influence of information technology. Therefore, higher educational institutions face the need to carry out not only fundamental and applied research, but also the development of progressive educational programs that would outstrip the current demand to search for new educational technologies and the introduction of new forms of the educational process management and activities in general in terms of content and informative fill-in.

The active development of the media has changed the didactic aspect and raised the general intellectual level of the audience. It indicates that at present, visual and screen images are dominant, and text is understood as information that is fixed in a sign, sound, and image. Therefore, it becomes relevant to study the transformation of methods for delivering information in the educational process. Since visual images carry the main semantic load, the main channels for information broadcasting are visual and audio visual. Influencing thinking and behaviour, they become the background of actual reality. Visualisation of the information environment is manifested in the development of modern culture.

Screen images and visual imagery are actively replacing textual reality, and therefore the wishes of the modern audience change, which in turn changes the way of perceiving the world and the thought process of the individual. Such a set of contemporary screen images (real, virtual), visual representation of data forms an educational information space, which today is based on the principles of media.

Analysis of recent studies and publications indicates the presence of works on visual culture. In particular, H. Ilina (2018) notes that: "Modern society is a society of mass production and consumption of visual images. Teaching and learning within knowledge engineering dynamics form visual literacy. In interaction with visual thinking, visual literacy forms a new system of cognitive capabilities of the individual, which are actively used in the processes of modern learning, teaching and creative activity" (p. 156). V. Solomatova explores the theoretical discourse of the approach associated with the visual shift and a new visual reality of culture. Features of the use of information technology in the educational process; use of distance learning technologies; attraction of media educational technologies, multimedia training tools;

N. Bilokonna, B. Hryvnaк, I. Dychkivska, S. Brammer, T. Clark, Y. Kundenko, Y. Siryi and others studied the innovative development of education in Ukraine. However, the influence of visual culture on the approaches and methods of educational technologies has not been studied enough.

■ **Purpose of the article**

The purpose of the article is to characterise the essence of visual culture in terms of audio visualisation and determine its influence on one of the critical areas of improving students' training in the modern educational process. The article covers the leading technologies, functions of audio visualisation, and analyses the feasibility of its use in higher education institutions. The article has analysed the case of the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts in introducing innovative technologies in the educational process.

The research methodology is based on the use of historical and theoretical analysis of pedagogical, philosophical, and art studies sources on the issue under study. Comparative and systematic approaches have helped to define visual culture as a factor in change and innovation shaping in the education system.

■ **Main research material**

Competition between different education systems is becoming a key factor in global competition, which requires constant updating of technologies, accelerated innovations' acquisition, quick adaptation to the demands and needs of a society that is changing dynamically. Therefore, a visually oriented society of virtual opportunities and information technologies actively applies the principle of visibility, which is one of the essential means in enhancing educational activities, the use of which ensures high results. Educational innovations and their implementation determine the future of education as a public institution. The rapid development of civilisation, undoubtedly, should be reflected in teaching (Siryi, 2010, p. 65-77).

Visual culture is a set of material and intellectual values in the field of visual media; it is a historically determined system of their reproduction and functioning in society. O. Malanchuk-Rybak (2013) notes that: "The phenomenon of visual culture is that it is formed under the conditions of an increasing speed of informative content transmission, a gradual clearing of language barriers and a constant confrontation between textual analysis and visual research" (p. 100). Yu. Trach reviews the content of visual culture concept in his research. She defines that: "The words "visual" and "visuality" (derived from the Latin "visualis" – "visual", from visus "sight" and videre "to see") have come into professional use relatively recently, in the last decade of the 20th century, and were used in a relatively narrow sense, for example, audio-visual technologies. Today, it is customary to name visual elements those elements of culture that are to some extent related to the technical culture of photography, cinema, video, and the Internet" (Trach, 2017, p. 170). As for the audience, visual culture acts as a system of levels for the development of a human personality capable of perceiving, analysing, evaluating visual media text, engaging in media creativity, assimilating new knowledge in the field of visual media.

According to the classification of audio-visual media, they are divided into:

1. Visual (visible) – drawings, tables, diagrams, reproductions of paintings, slide films, transparencies, etc.

2. Additive (auditory) – audio recordings, radio broadcasts, etc.

3. Audio-visual (visible and auditory) – cinema films, television films, slide films with sound, computer programs, etc. (Borysiuk, 2016, pp. 71-73).

O. B. Borysiuk provides its own classification of audio-visual training tools:

1. Sound recordings: all types of audio exercises, audio tests, the audio recording of texts, stories, audio lessons, and audio lectures.

2. Video recordings: video clips, video tutorials, video films, video lectures, thematic slides, etc.

3. Computer training tools: electronic textbooks, self-teachers, manuals, reference books, dictionaries, applied training, control programs, etc.

4. The Internet: network databases, video conferences, video broadcasts, virtual seminars, teleconferences, telecommunications projects, etc.

Visual culture predetermines the relevance and necessity of using audio-visual technologies in teaching, since audio-visual materials simplify the perception of information, contribute to better memorisation and understanding of the information received. Audio-visual training tools are a kind of tools that are most widely used in the educational process, including screen and audio tools designed to demonstrate visual and auditory information (Zaiets, 2019, p. 24). Audio-visual training tools play an important role in the educational process, since they have a significant impact on students; provide a figurative perception of the material and its visual detail in the most accessible form for perception and memorisation. Moreover, today audio-visual communications have put on a back burner the printed word, and screen forms of creativity are gradually replacing traditional ones.

Higher education institution today is a sociocultural space characterised by increased intensity of innovation processes. For Ukraine, the innovative potential of higher education can and should become a resource for a modernisation breakthrough (Pavlova, 2014, p. 248). It is known that the combination of various forms of information transfer (graphic, sound, visual) increases the effectiveness of studying. Most modern audio-visual means require special technical devices for presentation, for example, a computer, a multimedia projector, an interactive whiteboard, etc. Innovative technologies for the provision of educational services are becoming a means of effective activity for students in the context of fundamental changes in the organisation of the education system, methodology and technology of integral teaching and learning process management; strengthening the humanisation of education; study, generalisation and distribution of advanced native and foreign teaching experience (Naidonov & Khvalko, 2018).

The process of mastering audio-visual and information technologies is based on the principles of interdisciplinary integration. The use of audio-visual technologies in teaching should take into account the peculiarities of education informatisation, and the structure and content of audio-visual materials should be an integral part of the process-oriented training of future specialists. In general, audio-visual means in education provide the development of such skills and abilities as: the ability to receive information from various sources; the ability to use the audio-visual means;

ability to provide/present information in any way; the ability to analyse, evaluate the educational process; the ability to overthink own activities; the ability to solve didactic problems.

The use of audio-visual means in teaching should motivate to educational activities, contain the necessary information, increase interest in the topic, positively influence the formation and understanding of concepts, develop creative abilities, aesthetic interests of students. However, changes in the methods of presenting educational material primarily concern teachers, because they create the information base, model, choose a system of visualisation tools and use the necessary devices (computer programs, electronic textbooks, interactive whiteboards, multimedia projectors). The main element of the educational process is the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities to work with information, which should be developed and formed purposefully (Karabin, 2018, p. 132-135). The role of the modern teacher is essential for mediating between information sources of the latest technologies and the most effective form of teaching for the target audience. A Generation Z teacher must effectively use new information tools in solving professional problems. Thus, he is transformed into the creator of modern educational tools of a new generation, that is, he ceases to be a passive informatisation contemplator.

The University strives to provide not only teaching forms and methods but also training tools. Therefore, to improve the teaching and learning process, it offers students and teachers: computer and subject complexes, computer educational equipment, network and telecommunication equipment, screen-sound devices, equipped laboratories, a modern scientific library (includes not only the necessary equipment but also its own website, where there is an electronic catalogue, virtual reference, multimedia, virtual exhibitions, digital products, etc.), multimedia devices, video lectures, multimedia resources, etc. For example, the University scientific library “has practical experience in using many digital tools included in Top Tools for Learning 2019, using them in conducting intelligent gaming events. Genially and H5P formal learning tools from the “development resources” group and Kahoot! from the “classroom” group are used most often in the information and educational activities of the library” (Horban&Skachenko, 2020, p. 66-79).

The University surmises that it is the teacher who creates the conditions for informatisation; therefore, the institution organises various events aimed at popularising digital literacy and digital skills of the teaching staff. So, in March 2020, the Department of Computer Sciences conducted pieces of training for teachers in the format of a video conference “Digital tools for distance education”. During workshops in the lockdown, the participants discussed and visualised the expectations of distance education, learned about the services of the Google Suite for Education and the possibilities of using it at the University, tested several gamification interactive educational tools, as well as useful features of Google Classroom for teaching students (Digital week of KNUKiM, 2020). The University’s management understands that “a high level of mastering digital technologies presupposes the availability of creative skills for effective work in online apps and services, social networks and on web portals, creative presentation of information, its qualified collection, processing, arrangement, storage, analysis and knowledge extraction” (Humenchuk, 2020, p. 96).

The University aims to provide students with all the opportunities for receiving and processing information from traditional to the newest one. Along with the usual lectures, seminars, the institution conducts online quizzes (for example, the “Do you know Shevchenko?” educational online quiz (2019), organised by the Department of Philosophy and the Scientific Library of the University); webinars, which is an effective way to convey relevant information to students, as well as develop their practical knowledge and skills; online conferences; round tables; photo-, video exhibitions, etc. Materials of all teaching materials have been transferred into electronic form and made available for free access to students. Teachers offer not just textual information, but a full-fledged media resource for the discipline, filled with audio, video materials, and infographics. Online lectures are an example of such a transition from a traditional to an innovative form of information provision. In a short time (we are talking about the lockdown, when in March 2020, to prevent the spread of COVID-19 in Ukraine, all educational institutions were closed and distance education was introduced) teachers were able to adapt to distance education conditions and successfully implement educational activities. The 2020/2021 academic year at the University is organised based on Moodle (Modular Object-Oriented Distance Learning Environment) platform, which provides teachers, students and administrators with a large set of tools for computerised learning, including distance education (<https://sites.google.com/knukim.edu.ua>). Distance education is a powerful learning tool. In order to increase the effectiveness of new information technologies in teaching, a particular system should be formed, which provides a new understanding of the essence of learning, the role of the teacher and students in this process, the relationship between the teacher and students, and the equipping of workplaces (Prybylova, 2014, p. 28).

Today the educational process combines innovative and traditional technologies; modern software tools; informational resources; interaction of participants in the educational process in an open model of asynchronous individual learning; databases and knowledge; communication means (Sapohov, 2018, p. 53). Therefore, taking into account the events in the world and changes in the activities of all industries, our country initiates the transition to a blended form of education, which in turn will only strengthen the position of innovative, interactive forms of learning and the use of educational platforms. The Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine has prepared Recommendations for the introduction of blended learning in colleges and higher educational institutions, which explains the need for new approaches to learning, in particular the large-scale introduction of online technologies: “Toolkit for creating content using the educational platform usually ensures that teachers personally develop only basic objects in the form of HTML pages, tests, presentation, etc. However, even such work requires special technical means (graphic tablets, interactive whiteboards and multiboards, microphones, scanners, document cameras, graphic editors and other software). Interactive, multimedia content (graphic, video materials, simulators, etc.) is created in specialised environments by qualified specialists (designers, modellers, operators, programmers, etc.) using special-purpose hardware” (<https://mon.gov.ua/storage/app/media/vishcha-osvita/2020/>).

Considering the above mentioned, it can be argued that in the educational process, there is a steady tendency to move away from traditional pedagogical technologies and transition to new forms. The innovative technologies are based on the productive principle of mastering the material, which implies the rejection of templates, creative, meaningful, practical application, and reflection. This is explained by the increasing role of visuality in the formation of the social and cultural foundations of modern social experience, social order. The idea is also being developed that due to this there is a change in society (visuality gives rise to another sociality), an increase in new social knowledge (visual culture adequately reflects the new social order and organically integrates into the social picture of the world).

■ Conclusions

Thus, visual culture plays a significant role in forming public opinion and active subjectification of various forms of public activity. Modern society is impossible without visual culture, which has become an integral part of life, a universal communicator, an incentive for activity, a type of contemporary art, and a means of education. Therefore, the use of leading pedagogical technologies that provide effective technologies for processing, transferring, storing and using information is becoming very important for higher educational institutions. One of such technologies is audio visualisation as a means of personal self-realisation. It allows you to open not only new prospects for the development of methodological thought but also a wide range of opportunities for the application of innovative technologies in reality. Considering the format of information perception, audio-visual materials are considered one of the most effective and motivating means for interacting with the science world. Moreover, modern services help to achieve greater efficiency in the use of audio-visual tools in the educational process. Therefore, its involvement and competent use in the educational process is not only a time requirement, and also a complex but necessary process.

We consider that the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts has gained significant practical experience in using multiple digital tools through the use of modern digital technologies, conducting trainings and video conferences under quarantine conditions, using gamification interactive educational tools, as well as the capabilities of Google Classroom. The University has successfully combined traditional and innovative technologies; modern software tools, information resources and interaction of participants in the educational process. Teachers offer not only textual information, but a full-fledged media resource for the subject, filled with audio, video materials, infographics, etc.

The research does not review all aspects for the influence of visual culture on education, since visualisation technologies in the educational process, as well as determining the advantages and disadvantages of multimedia technologies for students of higher education, remain unexplored.

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■ ВІЗУАЛЬНА КУЛЬТУРА ЯК ЧИННИК ФОРМУВАННЯ ІННОВАЦІЙНИХ ТЕХНОЛОГІЙ НАВЧАННЯ: ДОСВІД КИЇВСЬКОГО НАЦІОНАЛЬНОГО УНІВЕРСИТЕТУ КУЛЬТУРИ І МИСТЕЦТВ

■ Кошелєва Оксана Борисівна

■ Старший викладач,

ORCID: 0000-0002-1653-2103, e-mail: renisenb@ukr.net,

Київський національний університет культури і мистецтва,

Київ, Україна

■ Анотація

Мета статті – схарактеризувати сутність візуальної культури та визначити її вплив на аудіовізуалізацію, проаналізувати доцільність її застосування у закладах вищої освіти. А також проаналізувати досвід Київського національного університету культури і мистецтв в запровадженні інноваційних технологій в навчальному процесі. Методологія дослідження базується на використанні історико-теоретичного аналізу педагогічних, філософських, мистецтвознавчих джерел з досліджуваної проблеми. Компаративний та системний підходи допомогли визначити візуальну культуру як чинник формування змін та інновацій в системі освіти. Наукова новизна полягає в дослідженні особливостей реалізації новітніх форм в навчальному процесі, що зумовлені змінами культурних пріоритетів. Висновки. Доведено, що візуальна культура, ставши невід’ємною частиною сучасного суспільства, універсальним комунікатором, стимулом діяльності, видом сучасного мистецтва, засобом освіти, відіграє помітну роль у формуванні суспільної думки та активної суб’єктивізації різних форм суспільної активності. Тому, нагальною потребою вищих навчальних закладів є використання провідних педагогічних технологій.

Одною з таких технологій є аудіовізуалізація, яка вважається одним з найефективніших та мотивуючих засобів, що дозволяють взаємодіяти зі світом науки. Тож, її залучення та грамотне використання в навчальному процесі є не лише вимогою часу, а й складним, проте необхідним процесом. Вважаємо, що Київський національний університет культури і мистецтв отримав значний практичний досвід використання цифрових інструментів завдяки використанню сучасних цифрових технологій, інтерактивних інструментів освітньої гейміфікації, можливості Google Classroom, проведенню тренінгів та відеоконференцій в умовах карантину; зумів вдало поєднати традиційні та інноваційні технології, сучасні програмні засоби, інформаційні ресурси та взаємодію учасників освітнього процесу.

▪ **Ключові слова:** візуальна культура; візуалізація; аудіовізуалізація; інтерактивні форми навчання; заклад вищої освіти

▪ **ВИЗУАЛЬНАЯ КУЛЬТУРА КАК ФАКТОР ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ОБУЧЕНИЯ: ОПЫТ КИЕВСКОГО НАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТА КУЛЬТУРЫ И ИСКУССТВ**

▪ **Кошелева Оксана Борисовна**

▪ *Старший преподаватель,*

ORCID: 0000-0002-1653-2103, e-mail: renisenb@ukr.net,

Киевский национальный университет культуры и искусств,

Киев, Украина

▪ **Аннотация**

Цель статьи – охарактеризовать сущность визуальной культуры и определить ее влияние на аудиовизуализацию, проанализировать целесообразность ее применения в учреждениях высшего образования. А также проанализировать опыт Киевского национального университета культуры и искусств во внедрении инновационных технологий в учебном процессе. Методология исследования базируется на использовании историко-теоретического анализа педагогических, философских, искусствоведческих источников по исследуемой проблеме. Компаративный и системный подходы помогли определить визуальную культуру как фактор формирования изменений и инноваций в системе образования. Научная новизна заключается в исследовании особенностей реализации новых форм в учебном процессе, которые обусловлены изменениями культурных приоритетов. Выводы. Доказано, что визуальная культура, став неотъемлемой частью современного общества, универсальным коммуникатором, стимулом деятельности, видом современного искусства, средством образования играет заметную роль в формировании общественной мысли и активного субъективизирования разных форм общественной активности. Поэтому, неотложной потребностью высших учебных заведений является использование ведущих педагогических технологий. Одной из таких технологий является аудиовизуализация, которая считается одним из самых

эффективных и мотивирующих средств, что позволяют взаимодействовать с миром науки. Поэтому, ее привлечение и грамотное использование в учебном процессе является не только требованием времени, но и сложным, однако необходимым процессом. Считаем, что Киевский национальный университет культуры и искусств получил значительный практический опыт использования цифровых инструментов благодаря использованию современных цифровых технологий, интерактивных инструментов образовательной геймификации, возможности Google Classroom, проведению тренингов и видеоконференций в условиях карантина; сумел удачно соединить традиционные и инновационные технологии, современные программные средства, информационные ресурсы и взаимодействие участников образовательного процесса.

■ **Ключевые слова:** визуальная культура; визуализация; аудиовизуализация; интерактивные формы обучения; учреждение высшего образования